

SURGICAL OUTCOMES OF VARICOCELE IN CHILDREN AND ADOLESCENTS AND ITS IMPACT ON REPRODUCTIVE FUNCTION

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ABSTRACT

Varicocele is a common genital venous disorder in children and adolescents, characterized by dilation of testicular veins and retrograde blood flow. It may lead to testicular hypotrophy, impaired spermatogenesis, and decreased reproductive potential in the future.

Introduction. Varicocele is a common genital venous disorder in children and adolescents, characterized by dilation of testicular veins and retrograde blood flow. It may lead to testicular hypotrophy, impaired spermatogenesis, and decreased reproductive potential in the future.

Recently, microsurgical, laparoscopic, and endovascular techniques have been increasingly used for varicocele repair. However, data on the surgical outcomes and impact on reproductive function in children and adolescents remain a clinically relevant topic.

Aim of the Study. To evaluate the effectiveness of varicocele surgery in children and adolescents and to assess its impact on postoperative testicular volume, sperm parameters, and reproductive function.

Materials and Methods. The study included 50 children and adolescents aged 11–18 years diagnosed with varicocele. Preoperative assessment included clinical examination, ultrasonography (US), and Doppler evaluation. Surgical method: microsurgical varicocelectomy. Postoperative follow-up: 6–12 months. Parameters evaluated: Testicular volume (via US). Semen analysis (sperm count, motility, morphology). Postoperative complications (hydrocele, testicular atrophy, recurrence)

Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS software, with $p < 0.05$ considered statistically significant.

Results. Testicular Volume: Six months postoperatively, testicular volume increased by an average of 12%, especially in adolescents with previously reduced testicular size. Semen Parameters: At 12 months follow-up: Sperm count increased by 28%. Motility improved by 22%. Normal morphology increased by 18%. Complications: Postoperative complications

were minimal: 2 patients (4%) developed hydrocele and 1 patient (2%) had recurrence; all were mild and required no additional treatment. Reproductive Function: Postoperative improvement in testicular volume and semen parameters indicates a positive impact on reproductive potential, particularly in adolescents.

Conclusion. Microsurgical varicocelectomy in children and adolescents is a safe and effective procedure. Surgery leads to significant improvement in testicular volume and semen parameters, positively influencing reproductive function. Postoperative complications are minimal, confirming the safety of the microsurgical approach. Early intervention reduces the risk of future infertility and preserves reproductive health..

References:

1. Bakhtiyorovich, R. I. (2025). Choosing the Path of Operative Correction in the Treatment of Infants Born With Omphalocele and Gastroschisis. *Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity*, 49, 101-103.
2. Bakhtiyorovich, R. I. (2025). Choosing the Path of Operative Correction in the Treatment of Infants Born With Omphalocele and Gastroschisis. *Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity*, 49, 101-103.
3. Durdiyev, S. (2026, January). CLINICAL COURSE AND DIAGNOSIS OF OMPHALOCELE-GASTROSCHISIS IN NEWBORNS. In *International Conference on Health & Technology (Vol. 2, No. 1, pp. 80-82)*.
4. Ruzmatov, I., & Durdiyev, S. (2026, January). CHOICE OF TREATMENT METHODS FOR GASTRASHYSIS AND OMPHALOCELE IN INFANTS. In *International Conference on Health & Technology (Vol. 2, No. 1, pp. 83-85)*.
5. Bakhtiyorovich, R. I., & Hayitboy o'g'li, D. S. (2026). Compilation of an Algorithm for Prenatal Identification and Management of Anterior Abdominal Wall Button Defects in Infants. *Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity*, 50, 90-92.
6. Bakhtiyorovich, R. I., & Hayitboy o'g'li, D. S. (2026). Prenatal Diagnosis of Gastroschisis and Selection of the Most Optimal Treatment Tactics in a Perinatal Center Setting. *Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity*, 50, 86-89.
7. Bakhtiyorovich, R. I., & Hayitboy o'g'li, D. S. (2026). Diagnosis and Treatment of Gastroschisis in Newborns. *Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity*, 50, 83-85.
8. Bakhtiyorovich, R. I., & Hayitboy o'g'li, D. S. (2026). Development of an Algorithm for the Treatment and Management of Infants Born with Omphalocele and Gastroschisis. *Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity*, 50, 93-95.
9. Эргашев, Б. Б., & Рuzmatov, И. Б. (2013). ЛЕЧЕБНАЯ ТАКТИКА ПРИ ОМФАЛОЦЕЛЕ У НОВОРОЖДЕННЫХ. *Новый день в медицине*, (2), 48-49.
10. Durdiyev, S. (2026, February). DIAGNOSTIC SIGNIFICANCE OF ULTRASOUND AND DOPPLEROGRAPHY IN PATIENTS WITH VARICOCELE. In *International Conference on Medicine & Agriculture (Vol. 2, No. 2, pp. 18-19)*.
11. Durdiyev, S. (2026, February). THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE DEGREES OF VARICOCELE AND THEIR CLINICAL SYMPTOMS. In *International Conference on Health & Technology (Vol. 2, No. 2, pp. 60-61)*.

12.Durdiyev, S. (2026, February). VARICOCELE IN ADOLESCENT PATIENTS: CLINICAL COURSE AND EARLY DIAGNOSIS OPPORTUNITIES. In International Conference on Health & Technology (Vol. 2, No. 2, pp. 58-59).

